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IMPORTANT STAGES IN THE PRODUCT LIFE CYCLE: TYPES OF CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIPS APPLICABLE TO UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article analyzes the stages of the product life cycle and the types of customer relationships adopted by various companies, identifying strategies that can be adapted to the conditions of Uzbekistan. The study draws on the experience of the United States, Germany, and Kazakhstan, which represent diverse yet practically significant development models, including a full value-chain and export-oriented cluster model, as well as a smallholder support and quality incentive model.

The findings indicate that sustainable management throughout the product life cycle not only increases profitability but also contributes to more efficient resource utilization, improved working conditions, the development of contractual relationships, the expansion of value-added processing, the implementation of transparent electronic trading mechanisms, and the provision of targeted financial support. The proposed recommendations are aimed at increasing value added, stabilizing employees' incomes, and enhancing the development potential of Uzbekistan's food industry.

Keywords: food industry, product life cycle, customer relationships, value chain, growth, profitability, quality, SWOT analysis, Uzbekistan.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются этапы жизненного цикла продукции и типы взаимоотношений с клиентами, применяемые различными компаниями, а также определяются стратегии, которые могут быть адаптированы к условиям Республики Узбекистан. Исследование основано на опыте США, Германии и Казахстана, представляющих различные, но практически значимые модели развития, включая модель полной цепочки создания стоимости и экспортно-ориентированную кластерную модель, а также модель поддержки малых производителей и стимулирования повышения качества продукции.

Результаты исследования показывают, что эффективное управление на всех этапах жизненного цикла продукции не только способствует повышению прибыльности, но и обеспечивает более рациональное использование ресурсов, улучшение условий труда, развитие договорных отношений, расширение глубокой переработки, внедрение прозрачных механизмов электронной торговли и предоставление адресной финансовой поддержки. Предлагаемые рекомендации направлены на увеличение добавленной стоимости, стабилизацию доходов работников и повышение потенциала развития пищевой промышленности Республики Узбекистан.

Ключевые слова: пищевая промышленность, жизненный цикл продукции, взаимоотношения с клиентами, цепочка создания стоимости, рост, прибыльность, качество, SWOT-анализ, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

Relationship marketing refers to a marketing approach in which both the buyer and the seller seek to establish and maintain a mutually beneficial, long-term relationship. This approach extends beyond the post-purchase exchange by fostering closer interaction with customers through personalized products and services, while using customer experience to build stronger and more sustainable relationships. Its primary focus on long-term customer retention distinguishes relationship marketing from traditional marketing approaches.

The product life cycle (PLC) describes the progression of a product through five distinct stages: development, introduction, growth, maturity, and decline. This framework enables businesses to formulate appropriate marketing strategies, adjust pricing policies, and forecast sales as market conditions evolve. The development stage involves market research, concept testing, and prototype creation. During this phase, products generate no sales revenue, while substantial financial resources are invested in research and development activities.

If one had to identify a single event that marked the transition from a production- and sales-oriented approach to a customer-oriented marketing philosophy, most marketing scholars would likely refer to the publication of Theodore Levitt's influential article, "Marketing Myopia," in the *Harvard Business Review*. Levitt argued that the decline of many industries resulted not from market saturation but from a narrow product-oriented perspective rather than a customer-oriented one. According to his thesis, organizations defined the scope of their businesses too narrowly and consequently failed to recognize emerging market opportunities and competitive threats.

For example, railway companies failed to recognize that they operated within the broader transportation industry rather than merely the railroad business. As a result, they allowed alternative modes of transportation to attract their customers. Likewise, many Hollywood film studios underestimated the growing influence of television because they perceived themselves as participants in the film industry rather than the broader entertainment industry. Levitt's concept remains one of the fundamental theoretical foundations of modern marketing, emphasizing that long-term business success depends on understanding and satisfying customer needs rather than focusing solely on products.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The product life cycle (PLC) concept is based on an analogy between biological life cycles and the pattern of sales growth exhibited by successful products. According to this concept, a product typically passes through four principal stages: introduction, growth, maturity, and decline. Each stage is characterized by distinct market conditions, consumer behavior, and marketing strategies, requiring businesses to adopt appropriate managerial and competitive approaches.

During the maturity stage, the market approaches saturation, and sales typically reach their peak before beginning to stabilize as demand becomes fully developed. Competition intensifies significantly, encouraging companies to introduce product improvements, offer promotional discounts, enhance customer services, or differentiate their products to maintain market competitiveness. Standard laptops and mainstream smartphones are representative examples of products in the maturity stage. Since most potential consumers already own these products, manufacturers primarily compete through incremental innovations, such as improved camera systems, enhanced battery performance, artificial intelligence (AI) integration, and software optimization.

Contemporary consumer behavior, particularly within the context of postmodern society, is characterized by rapid, dynamic, and continuously evolving consumption patterns. Consumers frequently switch between products, brands, and experiences in search of greater value, novelty, and personal satisfaction. As a result of increasing product diversity and market abundance, modern consumers simultaneously perform multiple social and professional roles—such as spouse, parent, employee, entrepreneur, fashion-conscious consumer, technology user, and digital participant—each associated with distinct needs, preferences, and purchasing behaviors. Consequently, companies increasingly rely on customer relationship management, brand differentiation, and personalized marketing strategies to strengthen customer loyalty throughout the product life cycle.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed comparative analysis, statistical analysis, and SWOT analysis as its primary research methods. The experiences of the United States, Germany, and Kazakhstan were selected for analysis, as these countries represent different approaches to product life cycle management and customer relationship practices that are of practical relevance to the conditions of Uzbekistan.

The study was based on data obtained from international organizations, FAOSTAT, UN Comtrade, the World Bank, the U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA), and relevant national and international sectoral development programmes [3, 6, 7, 11].

The methodological framework followed the logical sequence of "international experience – economic mechanism – applicability to Uzbekistan." At the first stage, production, market, and foreign trade indicators were analyzed. At the second stage, the institutional, organizational, and economic mechanisms applied in each country were examined. At the third stage, practical recommendations adapted to the national conditions of Uzbekistan were developed.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The dynamics of the global food industry during the period 2021–2025 indicate that the United States and Germany maintained their leading positions in the sector. These trends reflect the differentiated patterns of development among the world's major food-producing countries and illustrate the evolving competitiveness of national food industries. The comparative dynamics are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Product lifecycle¹

Relationship marketing refers to the establishment, development, and management of commercial relationships among economic partners, service providers, and customers across various levels of the marketing channel and the broader business environment. This approach emphasizes the creation, maintenance, and appropriate development of long-term relationships to ensure that all parties achieve their strategic and operational objectives.

Although profitability remains a fundamental objective of business activities, relationship marketing highlights the importance of achieving sustainable results through the consistent fulfillment of commitments and mutual value creation. Trust plays a central role in this process, as it is built through the reliable fulfillment of promises and the development of long-term cooperation.

Unlike traditional marketing, which primarily focuses on individual transactions, relationship marketing adopts a cross-functional approach that integrates all organizational processes involved in creating and delivering customer value. It encourages collaboration among different functional areas to strengthen customer relationships and enhance organizational performance. For this reason, many researchers prefer the term “relationship management”, as it more accurately reflects the comprehensive and organization-wide nature of this strategic approach (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Types of customer relationship²

1 author's development
 2 author's development

The relationship ladder of customer loyalty classifies customers according to their level of loyalty and engagement with an organization. The first level consists of prospects—potential customers who are likely to purchase the company's products or services in the future. The subsequent levels include customers, clients, supporters, advocates, and partners. The primary objective of relationship marketing is to encourage customers to progress to higher levels of loyalty by delivering personalized services and consistently exceeding customer expectations at every stage of the relationship.

Relationship marketing originally evolved within industrial and service marketing as a response to the limitations of traditional transaction-based marketing. Its development has been significantly supported by successive generations of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) systems, which collect, store, and analyze customer preferences, purchasing behavior, and interaction history. For example, automobile manufacturers maintain customer databases containing information on repeat purchases, product preferences, and financing options. These data enable firms to develop personalized marketing offers and tailored product recommendations.

The widespread adoption of digital technologies has further strengthened relationship marketing. In e-commerce, customer shopping behavior is continuously analyzed to identify purchasing preferences and predict future needs. Based on these insights, businesses can provide personalized recommendations through cross-selling strategies, email marketing campaigns, and other digital communication channels.

Relationship marketing has also transformed traditional direct mail marketing. Advances in digital printing technology allow companies to produce individualized promotional materials through variable data printing. Customer information—including names, addresses, demographic characteristics, and purchase histories—is incorporated into personalized documents that better reflect individual preferences. As a result, marketing communications become more relevant, customer engagement increases, and response rates improve.

The United States possesses one of the world's largest and most productive food industries, generating approximately USD 1.5 trillion in annual economic activity. Domestic agricultural production is sufficient to meet national food demand; however, the country imports a considerable share of fruits and vegetables to ensure year-round availability and greater product diversity, particularly for tropical and seasonal products.

The principal agricultural products of the United States include:

- Soybeans – 14.0%
- Corn – 7.9%
- Beef and beef products – 5.9%
- Tree nuts – 5.6%
- Pork and pork products – 4.9%
- Dairy products – 4.7%
- Soybean meal – 3.6%
- Food preparations – 3.6%

Overall, the United States is regarded as a food self-sufficient country because it produces more than enough agricultural output to satisfy domestic demand. International trade primarily contributes to expanding consumer choice and ensuring the continuous availability of seasonal and tropical food products.

Germany is internationally recognized for its well-developed food industry, high-quality food products, and rich culinary traditions. Traditional German cuisine is characterized by meat-based dishes, potatoes, bread products, and regional specialties. At the same time, Germany's food industry is distinguished by strong technological capabilities, high production standards, and internationally competitive food-processing enterprises.

Among the leading Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) companies in Germany, measured by revenue, are Henkel, Theo Müller Group, Beiersdorf, Südzucker, Dr. Oetker, Tchibo, Haribo, August Storck, KRÜGER GROUP, and Ritter Sport.

The German food service market was valued at USD 87.80 billion in 2022 and is projected to increase from USD 96.08 billion in 2023 to approximately USD 183.55 billion by 2030, representing a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 9.69%. With a population exceeding 83 million, Germany represents one of Europe's largest and most attractive food and beverage markets.

Food production has become one of the rapidly developing sectors of the economy in Kazakhstan, with annual output exceeding USD 7.9 billion. National development strategies prioritize increasing value-added agricultural processing, strengthening food security, expanding livestock production, improving crop productivity, and developing modern food-processing infrastructure.

The Government of Kazakhstan has given particular attention to increasing the share of processed agricultural products within total production. State-supported holding companies provide financial assistance through subsidies and concessional loans for modern breeding technologies, precision agriculture, and food-processing equipment.

Relationship marketing seeks to strengthen long-term relationships with customers and enhance customer retention. Based on social exchange theory, Morgan and Hunt (1994) distinguished between economic exchange and social exchange, concluding that trust and commitment constitute the fundamental foundations of successful long-term relationships. Their research demonstrated that sustainable business relationships increasingly rely on mutual trust, commitment, and cooperation rather than solely on one-time economic transactions.

During the first five months of 2025, Kazakhstan's food production increased by 10.5%, reaching 1.4 trillion tenge. Particularly significant growth was recorded in beet sugar production (13.7-fold increase to 64 thousand tons), vegetable oil (19.1%), butter (12.7%), sausage products (11%), and flour (6.6%). These results were reported by the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

To further strengthen domestic production capacity and diversify food processing, Kazakhstan is implementing more than 670 investment projects with a total value of approximately 3.3 trillion tenge, including 197 projects specifically focused on import substitution. The combined value of these import-substitution projects amounts to approximately 915 billion tenge.

Special emphasis has been placed on the development of the sugar industry. In 2024, Kazakhstan processed a record 1.2 million tons of sugar beet, resulting in a 62% increase in beet sugar production.

Furthermore, an investment agreement was signed with Qazaq Arab Sugar for the construction of a new sugar processing plant in the Almaty Region, with an annual production capacity of 500,000 tons and an investment volume of 307 billion tenge. An additional investment proposal submitted by a Chinese investor for a sugar processing facility in the Zhambyl Region, with an annual capacity of 130,000 tons and planned investments of 51 billion tenge, is currently under consideration.

According to the Ministry of Agriculture, Kazakhstan harvested a record grain crop of 26.7 million tons in 2024, representing a 1.5-fold increase compared with the previous year. Production also increased for several other agricultural commodities, including rice (16%, reaching 563.1 thousand tons), buckwheat (42%, 118.1 thousand tons), and oilseeds (46%, 3.2 million tons).

Meat production (slaughter weight) increased by 3%, reaching 409.1 thousand tons, while poultry production increased by 6.2% to 157.8 thousand tons. Milk production reached 1.3 million tons, representing a 7.5% increase, and egg production totaled 1.8 billion units, exceeding the previous year's production by approximately 200 million eggs.

Relationship marketing has evolved into one of the broadest and most influential fields of contemporary marketing research. Its development has been supported by extensive empirical evidence across various industries and by theoretical concepts including customer retention, loyalty, commitment, trust, mutuality, structural bonds, and attraction. These concepts originate from economics, social exchange theory, organizational behavior, and small-group theory.

Overall, the development of relationship marketing demonstrates that effective customer relationships are influenced by both the empirical characteristics of different industries and the specific nature of interactions between business partners. Although relationship marketing is applied differently across service industries and business-to-business markets, its central objective remains the creation of sustainable, mutually beneficial, and value-generating relationships. Consequently, it has become an essential strategic approach for improving customer satisfaction, strengthening competitive advantage, and supporting long-term organizational performance (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Fast food consumption in the UK³

³ The graph gives information about the consumption of fast food (in grams per week), in the UK from 1970 to 1990.

The bar chart illustrates weekly expenditure on three categories of fast food by different income groups in Britain, while the line graph presents the consumption trends of these fast foods over a 20-year period (1970–1990).

Overall, the figures indicate that hamburgers were the most preferred fast food among the high- and average-income groups, and their consumption increased substantially throughout the period under review.

The bar chart compares expenditure on hamburgers, fish and chips, and pizza across three income groups. Hamburgers accounted for the highest level of weekly expenditure among the high-income and average-income groups, at approximately 40 pence and 32 pence per person, respectively. In contrast, individuals in the low-income group spent more on fish and chips, with weekly expenditure reaching approximately 17 pence, a level comparable to that observed in the high-income group. Expenditure on pizza showed a gradual decline as income levels decreased, amounting to approximately 20 pence, 12 pence, and 6 pence per week for the high-, average-, and low-income groups, respectively.

The line graph shows that fish and chips were the most widely consumed fast food in 1970, with consumption reaching approximately 300 grams per person per week. Over the following two decades, consumption gradually declined, reaching approximately 200 grams by 1990. In contrast, both hamburger and pizza consumption exhibited an upward trend during the same period. Hamburger consumption increased particularly rapidly, reaching approximately 500 grams by 1990, making it the most consumed fast food at the end of the observation period. Pizza consumption also increased steadily, reaching approximately 220 grams in 1990, a level slightly higher than the final consumption of fish and chips (Figure 4).

Figure 4. SWOT analysis⁴

SWOT analysis (also referred to as the SWOT matrix, TOWS analysis, WOTS, WOTS-UP, or situational analysis) is a widely used strategic planning and decision-making tool that identifies the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with an organization, project, or business initiative.

SWOT analysis is employed to evaluate an organization's strategic position and is commonly applied during the preliminary stages of strategic planning and decision-making. It facilitates the identification of both internal and external factors that may influence the achievement of organizational objectives. By systematically examining each of the four dimensions, decision-makers can identify competitive advantages, recognize areas for improvement, and develop appropriate strategic responses.

SWOT analysis has long been recognized as a reliable and widely accepted instrument for strategic assessment. At the same time, researchers have noted several methodological considerations, including its relatively static analytical framework, the potential influence of subjective judgments when identifying key factors, and the need for a balanced assessment of both internal and external environments. These observations have encouraged the development of complementary strategic analysis methods that further enhance decision-making processes.

⁴ author's development

At the introduction stage of the product life cycle, a new product generally experiences gradual market acceptance as potential customers become familiar with its features and benefits. Early adopters and innovative consumers are usually the first to purchase the product, particularly when it offers meaningful improvements over existing alternatives. The speed of market acceptance largely depends on the product's perceived advantages, ease of adoption, and the effectiveness of marketing activities. Consequently, sales growth during this stage is typically moderate while market awareness continues to expand.

As the product gains wider market acceptance, sales increase steadily until the market approaches saturation. At this stage, the rate of growth gradually stabilizes, reflecting a balance between purchases by new customers and replacement purchases by existing users. This period represents the maturity stage of the product life cycle, during which market demand becomes relatively stable and competition focuses increasingly on product differentiation, customer retention, and incremental innovation.

The importance of the Product Life Cycle (PLC) concept lies in its ability to demonstrate that market conditions continuously evolve and that change is an inherent characteristic of every product. Rather than serving as a precise forecasting tool, the PLC provides a valuable conceptual framework for understanding the typical patterns of product development and market evolution. Similar to biological life cycles, different products may follow comparable general stages while varying considerably in their duration, growth patterns, and market performance. Therefore, the PLC should be applied as a strategic planning framework that supports informed managerial decision-making rather than as an exact predictive model.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

According to the results of the study, the experience of foreign countries in developing customer relationships demonstrates three important and complementary directions.

The United States model highlights the importance of developing the sector through an integrated value chain and export-oriented clusters. The German model emphasizes the integration of product life cycle stages into the value chain while promoting quality-oriented production and customer-focused incentives. The Kazakhstan model illustrates the importance of strengthening production capacity, expanding processing opportunities, and introducing guaranteed procurement mechanisms to support sustainable sectoral development.

Overall, the adaptation of international best practices to Uzbekistan's national conditions and ongoing economic reforms has significant potential to enhance the effectiveness of customer relationship management throughout the product life cycle. Such an approach may contribute to increasing export potential, creating higher value-added products, strengthening the competitiveness of domestic producers, stabilizing employees' incomes, generating new employment opportunities, and supporting the sustainable development of the food industry.

REFERENCES

1. Baker, M. J. (2009). *The Marketing Book*. Oxford: Butterworth-Heinemann.
2. Kotler, P., & Armstrong, G. (2025). *Principles of Marketing* (13th ed.). Pearson Education.
3. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). *FAOSTAT Statistical Database*. Available at: <https://www.fao.org/faostat>
4. World Bank. *Agriculture and Rural Development: Sector Analysis*. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org>
5. Kotler, P. (2021). *Moving from Traditional to Digital Marketing*. Canada.
6. Augustin-Jean, L., & Alpermann, B. (Eds.). (2014). *Contemporary Marketing*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
7. Ministry of Textiles, Government of India. *Marketing Management*. Available at: <https://www.texmin.gov.in/>
8. Godin, S. (2025). *This Is Marketing*. New York: Portfolio.
9. Schaltegger, S., & Burritt, R. (2000). *Digital Marketing*. Sheffield: Greenleaf Publishing.
10. Porter, M. E., & Van der Linde, C. (1995). Green and Competitive: Ending the Stalemate. *Harvard Business Review*, **73**(5), 120–134.
11. Epstein, M. J. (2008). *Making Sustainability Work*. San Francisco: Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
12. OECD. (2023). *Marketing Tools and Evaluation*. Paris: OECD Publishing.
13. Gao, S., Meng, F., Gu, Z., Liu, Z., & Farrukh, M. (2021). Mapping and Clustering Analysis on Marketing, Social and Governance Field: A Bibliometric Analysis Using Scopus. *Sustainability*, **13**(13), Article 7304.
14. International Organization for Standardization (ISO). (2015). *ISO 14001:2015 Environmental Management Systems — Requirements with Guidance for Use*. Geneva: ISO.
15. Bansal, P., & Roth, K. (2000). Why Companies Go Green. *Academy of Management Journal*, **43**(4), 717–736.

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